

TAMPERE UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Finnish universities are required by national law to have gender equality (GE) and diversity plans (the law requires any organisation employing more than 30 people to have a GE plan and a diversity plan). These plans initially covered mostly gender equality issues and later increasingly also dealt with diversity issues. A national report found that only 45% of universities had their plans up to date, in conformity with the legislative requirement that the plan be updated every second year.¹ The plans also often miss certain required sections, such as an assessment of measures implemented in the previous period.²

The Act on Equality between Women and Men, Section 6, lists a number of areas that an employer is required to act upon and prevent. These include gender-based discrimination, including sexual and gender harassment. Most of the gender equality and diversity plans of Finnish universities deal with sexual and/or gender harassment in some way – for example, by referring to a code of conduct or certain procedures and having harassment contact persons in place.³ However, these references may be very general in the plans and may not be accompanied by any concrete measures or evaluations.

¹ Tanhua, I. (2020). *Report on the promotion of gender equality and non-discrimination in higher education institutions*. Publications of the Ministry of Education and Culture. Finland 2020:24.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid, p. 50.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

Tampere University has an Equality and Non-Discrimination Policy 2021-2022. The policy is more generally about equality, equity, and diversity. Sexual and gender harassment (offline and online) prevention, monitoring, and assessment are treated as part of the gender equality, equity, and diversity policy and work.

URLs

- › Equality and Non-Discrimination Policy 2021-2022:
www.tuni.fi/sites/default/files/2021-06/tasy_suunnitelma_2021-2022_tau_eng.pdf

Entry into force: 2021

TRAINING

The Equal Opportunities Committee organises training and events for discussing equality and non-discrimination issues. Tampere University supports the building of diversity awareness and age management skills, and prevents discrimination by offering professional development opportunities and staff training. For example, training on diversity management will be provided to leaders and supervisors, and training on equality, equity, and diversity in recruiting to those involved in recruiting.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

There are some researchers who are working on GBV-related topics, and the university was active in some GBV-related topics and events in mid-2000, but there seems to be less activity around these topics now (besides the #MeToo event).

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: Sexual harassment, gender harassment, organisational violence, and gender-based bullying, as well as the online forms of these behaviours.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: 4Ps are covered – prevalence, prevention, protection, partnership (with the student union TREY).

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: The policy is aimed at academic staff, non-academic staff, and students.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes: ‘The University is also committed to preventing multiple discrimination, which occurs when a person is discriminated against for more than one reason.’

Specific vulnerable groups: Staff and students with disabilities.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No. No statistics are compiled of harassment cases to protect privacy. However, the University has an Equal Opportunities Committee which is responsible for monitoring the implementation of this policy and for taking steps to promote equality across the university. The Equal Opportunities Committee will monitor and assess the achievement of objectives every two years and will report to the university management. This policy and the monitoring of this policy will help to ensure that the university’s activities meet appropriate quality standards.

Evaluation: Yes. The Equal Opportunities Committee will assess the achievement of objectives and the implementation of the agreed measures, and draw up a report when this policy expires. The Equal Opportunities Committee will present the report to the Management Group of Tampere University, which will comment on the development measures that are proposed by the Equal Opportunities Committee based on the report.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

There is no institutional procedure for reporting and investigation. However, instructions for responding to inappropriate behaviour are available for both students and staff on the intranet, and students are advised to contact academic advisory staff for more information. Online material includes guidelines on how to act and what to do in situations of sexual and gender-based harassment, inappropriate conduct, harassment, and bullying, and on dealing with harassment, hate speech, and controversies on social media. The Student Union has its own guidelines and contact persons that are available online.⁴

Staff and students can send ideas and comments relating to activities to promote equality and non-discrimination by e-mail to the Equal Opportunities Committee. They are also invited to contact the Equal Opportunities Committee with any questions or issues relating to equality and non-discrimination.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Charlotta Niemistö in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

⁴ <https://trey.fi/en/advocacy/help-regarding-harassment-discrimination-and-bullying>

